

Organizational Identification as an Approach to Achieve Outstanding University Performance: A Study on Sadat City University

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Abstract:

This paper tries to identify the impact of Organizational Identification (OI) on Outstanding University Performance (OUP) at Sadat City University (SCU). Using Cheney, 1982; and Reese, 2014 for measuring OI and Kotler, 2000 for measuring OUP. About 400 survey questionnaires were distributed. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 75%.

The research has reached a number of results which are: (1) the general average of the areas of OI among the different categories of faculty members at the University of Sadat City is high. The organizational membership as one of the dimensions of OI ranked first, followed by organizational loyalty in the second place, and finally the organizational similarity in the third place as one of the dimensions of OI at SCU, (2) the general average of the areas of job performance among the various categories of faculty members at SCU is high. The beneficiaries as one of the dimensions of OUP ranked first, followed by the organizational culture in the second place, the resources in the third place, and finally the process as one of the dimensions of OUP at SCU, and (3) there is a statistically significant relationship between the areas of OI (OL, OS and OM), and OUP (beneficiaries, process, resources and organizational culture) at SCU.

The study referred to a number of recommendations which are: (1) designing and implementing a set of training programs for all officials at SCU to maintain the level of OI among faculty members, and this can be done through the development of awareness among administrative leaders of the concept and importance and areas of OI and its positive effects both at the level of faculty member, or at the university level, (2) the officials at SCU maintain the level of OI, and can be done by increasing interest in faculty members, and meet their needs and desires periodically to achieve and satisfy the possible ones, (3) the officials at SCU should increase the level of OI among faculty members, and can be done by inviting members of the faculty to participate in decision-making by providing their views and suggestions, (4) directing the attention of officials at SCU to strengthen the OI among faculty members, and can be done through meetings and meetings, and the practice of social and recreational activities, (5) the officials at SCU should maintain on the level of performance of all members of the faculty, and to support and strengthen the strengths, and address the causes of weakness and weakness and work to avoid them in the future, and (6) directing the attention of officials at SCU should maintain the level of OI among faculty members, and can be done through the creation of working conditions, and follow the method of incentives, whether physical or moral, and the design of incentive systems conditional on performance, as the incentives play an important role in maintaining the level of OI on the one hand and positively affecting the level of functional performance on the other.

1. Introduction

OI plays an important role in the decision-making process of an organization. When an individual evaluates alternative options, it does not only take into consideration his personal goals but also takes into account the objectives of his organization (Duncan, 2002).

OI is a form of social identification. The organizations seek to the link between the vision, mission and organization staff in a way that contributes to their goals efficiently and effectively (Simon, 2000).

OI plays an important role for the individual in terms of the benefits that an individual achieves through symmetry: the promotion of self-esteem, transcendence, the meaning of life, the increase of ambition, belonging. (Mael & Ashforth, 2001). OI provides organizations with many benefits such as commitment, motivation, performance, and organizational citizenship, as well as minimizing cases of monopoly and conflict (Dessler, 1999).

The sense of OI may prevent the employee from becoming distressing. Parity can be seen as a precondition for a general sense of conviction, and individuals who are represented with the organization are expected to remain in the organization and make an effort to improve the organization (Dutton et al., 1994).

Organizations seek different types and sizes to achieve their vision and mission. Hence, the organization works to ensure that its employees work with this vision and mission so that their goals meet the objectives of the organization. When an individual feels psychological and social links to the organization in which he or she works, this is called organizational symmetry (Johnson et al., 1999).

OI is one of the topics that require further research, investigation, and analysis. OI is an important part of the organizational culture and is one of the social variables that the organization seeks to achieve in order to increase organizational affiliation and loyalty (Mael & Ashforth, 1992; Stuart, 1999).

Although the subject of OI is of interest to a number of researchers in organizations (Simon, 2000), it has played an important role in regulatory research (Burgi & Roos, 2002) because of its positive effects both at the individual and organization level (Abrams, et. al., 1998; Tyler, 1999).

From the point of view of the individual, there are many benefits that can be achieved by the individual through OI, and these benefits in the promotion of self-esteem, self-transcendence, and superiority, and to make sense of the life of the individual, and improve the level of ambition of individuals (Mael & Ashforth, 2001).

At the organizational level, it gains numerous benefits through OI, such as increasing the degree of individual commitment (Kogut & Zander, 1996; Foreman & Whetten, 2002), increasing the coherence of personnel in the organization, cooperation, participation, and coordination (Kogut & Zander, 1996), increasing the degree to which employees relate to the values and objectives of the organization (Hant & Morgan, 1994), increased work effort (Bartel, 2001), the low turnover of the organization (Mael & Ashforth, 1995), increasing individuals' motivation towards organizational goals (Werchel, et al., 1998), increasing the level of job satisfaction of individuals working in the organization (Hogg et al., 1995), and deepening the behavior of organizational citizenship (Dutton, et al., 1994), improving the level of functionality of the employees (Fiol & Huff, 1992).

OI has a significant impact on OUP. In other words, there is a positive relationship between OI and OUP. It is worth noting that the better the relationship between employees, the greater the level of OUP (Katrinli et al., 2008). Social responsibility plays an important role in achieving OI, which has an impact on OUP (Carmeli et al., 2007). OI has multiple effects on OUP (Chughtai & Buckley, 2010). OI as an independent variable has positive effects on OUP as a dependent variable (Liu et al., 2011).

In the light of the above, this research seeks to identify the level of OI in the area of loyalty (support for the university), the field of similarity (recognition of common characteristics), and the area of organizational membership (sense of belonging) and its impact on the level of organizational performance. The higher the level of OI, the more complete the tasks and duties assigned to them and this increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization in achieving its objectives (Katrinli et al., 2008; Fiol & Huff, 1992; Liu et al., 2011; Chughtai & Buckley, 2010).

2. Organizational Identification

The foot was the first to use the term identification in the organizational context in 1951, and Foot considered that identification is an essential element in motivating individuals. Foot views OI as dependence and commitment to the organization's identity. In his view, OI is the individual's view of oneself as a member of the organization, and this pays the individual to act on behalf of the organization (Bartels, 2006).

The areas of psychology and organizational behavior are the basis for the concept of OI and have roots in the theory of social identity (Woratschek et al., 2010).

At present, most research in OI focuses on social identity theory, as individuals classify themselves as social groups such as organizational membership, gender, age group, etc. (Jones et al., 2010). OI plays an important role in influencing the individual and the organization. The theory of social identity has shown that the realization of class identity leads to the individual's bias toward his group, which in turn leads to his cohesion with the group to which he belongs by forming commonalities that are perceived with other members (Cassani, 2007).

The researchers have shown that when an individual is strongly associated with the organization in which he or she works, it is due to the group's cognitive characteristics to itself, and the organization becomes, to a certain extent, part of itself and therefore likely to show a positive tendency towards it (Ashforth & Mael, 1989).

OI contributes to improved feedback, as we note that individuals who are similar to the organization become more interested in the specific issues of the organization in which they work such as the organization's reputation and the persistence and continued organizational success (Cassani, 2007).

OI is one of the new forms of social symmetry, where organizations seek different work to be committed to their mission and to the vision they aim to achieve (Simon, 2000).

The process of identification can be described by the fact that the employee is associated with a particular organization, and this is illustrated by several questions: (1) Does the employee consider the goals of the organization to be the same as the goals he has? (2) Does the employee salute and strengthen the organization in which he works if he is out of work? (Duncan, 2002).

It can be said that the term OI is originally a political term rooted in the political theory that has largely focused on the similarity of the masses (Johnson et al., 1965).

OI is that employees who are similar to their organizations re-shape their own self-concepts to accommodate the concepts and values of the organization (Tompkin & Cheney, 1985).

OI is the process of union with or belonging to an organization (Jones & Voipe, 2010).

OI is the degree to which a worker in the organization defines for himself the same characteristics that the organization believes to be known or described, which can be positive or negative (Milton & Westphal, 2005).

OI is the question of who I am for the organization? Or what is my relationship with the organization? (Edwards, 2005).

OI is the psychology of the relationship between the individual and the organization so that the individual feels himself and the depth of the relationship with the organization as a social entity (Johnson et al., 1999).

OI is the connection of the worker to his or her destiny, as illustrated by (1) whether the individual considers the goals of the organization to be the same as the goals he or she owns? (2) Does the individual praise the organization if he is out of work? (Duncan, 2002).

OI consists of several methods, the most important of which are the similarity of the values and objectives shared by individuals and the organization. The other and more recent way of forming the concept of symmetry is with the help of social identity theory (Carol, 2001).

OI is the perception of the individual and his or her union with the organization in which he or she works, and identifies himself. OI includes the following dimensions (Cheney, 1982; Reese, 2014):

1. **Organizational Similarity (OS)** refers to an exchange in understanding the common goals and desires of other members of the organization. OS system is the awareness of an individual's characteristics, values, and goals shared with other members of the organization.
2. **Organizational Membership (OM)** is the degree to which the concept of self is linked to the organization. OM is the degree of the concept of the individual itself in terms of its association with the organization, and that it is a sense of belonging and a sense of attachment and emotional attraction, and self-definition through organizational membership in the organization.
3. **Organizational Loyalty (OL)** is the extent to which the worker supports the organization and its defense. OL is loyalty to the organization and enthusiasm to achieve its objectives and to defend and support and simulate the behavior of other members

3. Outstanding University Performance

OUP is derived from "to perform" which means "doing work, achieving a mission or realizing a given activity. It is a reflection of the organization's ability and aptitude to realize its goals (Eccles, 1991).

OUP is the organization's ability to achieve its long-term goals (Robins & Wiersema, 1995) which exceeds average normal performance, as well as being part of the excellent performance (Privett, 1983).

OUP is the determinant of its existence. The decline in OUP may lead to organizational death (Baum & Singh, 1994), a situation that occurs when the institution fails, close its operations and disintegrates its components (Carroll & Delacroix, 1982).

Despite a large number of research and studies on OUP, no agreement was found on the concept of OUP. Despite this difference, most researchers express their exams through the success of the organization in achieving its objectives.

OUP is a reflection of the ability of the organization to achieve its objectives, especially the long-term objectives (Miller & Broamiley, 1990).

OUP is the capacity of an organization that is used efficiently and effectively to achieve its objectives (Collis & Montgomey, 1995). It is the output level of the organization after operations are performed on its inputs. Also, it is the output of activities occurring within the organization (Wit & Meyer, 1998).

After reviewing the different concepts of OUP, it can be argued that OUP is the desired results which the organization seeks to achieve efficiently and effectively.

Organizations that attempt to realize OUP have their own characteristics that turn them different from conventional performance (Kotler, 2000).

There are three dimensions of OUP. They are beneficiaries, processes, resources, and organizational culture (Kotler, 2000). These dimensions can be illustrated as follows:

1. **Beneficiaries:** organizations should identify persons of interest and needs. They include beneficiaries, employees, suppliers, and distributors. The organization must satisfy the minimum expectations for each group so as to be distinct in its performance.
2. **Processes:** organizations that attempt to achieve user satisfaction cannot achieve this without effective operations. High performance organizations are those that focus on developing new products and attracting the beneficiaries to retain them.
3. **Resources:** organizations need resources to implement their operations and must own or control these resources to maintain their privileged status. May receive such resources from outside the Organization; the most important resource to be paid attention is human resources.
4. **Organizational Culture (OC):** the organization consists of structures, policies, and cultures. The critical feature of these components is rapid change. It is noted that construction and policies do not change, while OC is more difficult to change. The interest of institutions in providing a high culture helps employees to achieve outstanding performance levels.

4. Research Model

The research model is presented in Figure (1). It shows that the independent variable is OI. Also, the dependent variable is OUP. The research model is presented in the following figure (1).

The research framework suggests that OI has an impact on OUP at SCU. OI is measured in terms of OL, OS, and OM (Cheney, 1982). OUP is measured in terms of beneficiaries, processes, resources, and OC (Kotler, 2000).

Figure (1)
The Research Model

5. Research Questions

The researcher reached to the research problem through two sources. The first is the previous studies that dealt with the relationship between OI and OUP. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment in general and SCU in particular.

The literature review of OI has shown that there is a significant impact of OI on job satisfaction (Khosravi et al., 2013). There is a strong relationship between OI and OC. The study also indicated that there is a correlation between OI and organizational commitment (Lee, 2013).

One study also indicated that the greater the similarity between individuals, the higher the degree of job satisfaction (Boenigk & Helmig, 2013). One study found that OI has positive effects on employee performance. The study also indicated that OI contributes to increasing the role of organizational citizenship behavior (Liu et al., 2011).

One study indicated that OI has multiple effects on job performance (Chughtai & Buckley, 2010) while another study showed that there is a positive relationship between supervision and OI, meaning that the better the relationship between supervisor and employees, the greater the level of OI between them (Katrinli et al., 2008).

One study found that the communication climate indirectly affects the level of OI (Bartels et al., 2006). One study found that there was a statistically significant relationship between OI and organizational commitment (Gautam et al., 2005).

In addition, there is a positive correlation between OI and organizational citizenship behavior, meaning that the greater the level of OI, the greater the voluntary work in the organization (Bellou et al., 2005).

Finally, another study indicates that there is no relationship between OI and job satisfaction. The study also indicated that there is a weak correlation between OI and job satisfaction and absence of faculty members (Knippenberg & Schie, 2000).

As for OUP, literature has shown that there is a positive relationship between organizational commitment and OUP. The study also indicated that male workers are better at performance than their female (Memari et al., 2013).

The study also found that there is a relationship between the performance of faculty member and total quality management in the educational process (Peleyeju & Ojebivi, 2013).

Private university faculty members feel more comfortable than their counterparts in government institutions with regard to financial rewards, perhaps because private institutions are well funded (Mbon et al., 2012).

Another study showed that the climate in government universities is good, with communications and resources available effectively. The regulatory climate also plays an important role in influencing performance (Olorunsola & Arogundade, 2012).

One study also suggested that university administration should pay more attention to the provision of physical facilities, information services, motivation, participation in decision-making, and staff development in order to facilitate better work of faculty (Ajayi et al., 2011).

Participation in the decision-making process and degree will have a significant impact on faculty performance (Sukirno & Siengthai, 2011).

In addition, OI has a significant impact on job performance. The nature of supervision contributes significantly to OI (Katrinli et al., 2008).

One study found that social responsibility plays an important role in achieving OI, which has an impact on OUP (Carmeli et al., 2007).

Another study pointed out that the first goal of the students is to improve the effectiveness of teaching and to obtain better results through the development of teaching methods, teaching methods used in the teaching process, and development and improvement of the university book (Chen & Hoshower, 2003).

Finally, another study indicated that students' assessment of the effectiveness of the faculty member's performance should be cumulative in order to be analyzed, which makes this information a scientific and managerial reference that influences how best to use faculty members in courses that fit their personal characteristics (Marsh, 2001).

The second source to determine the research problem is the pilot study which was conducted with 30 employees at SCU to identify the dimensions of OI and OUP. The researcher found several indicators which explain the importance of OI in affecting OUP at SCU. The research questions are as follows:

Q1: What is the statistical relationship between OI (OL) and OUP at Sadat City University?

Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between OI (OS) and OUP at Sadat City University?

Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between OI (OM) and OUP at Sadat City University?

6. Research Hypotheses

The literature review of OI has shown that control, socialization plays an important role in influencing OI. The study also pointed out that socialization mediates the relationship between control and OI (Hung-Wen, 2013). In addition, psychological empowerment as a variable mediates the relationship between OI and job satisfaction (Prati & Zani, 2013). There is also a strong relationship between organizational identity and OI. The study also indicated that OI mediates the relationship between trust and organizational identity (Tuzun & Çağlar, 2009). There is also a positive relationship between organizational justice and OI (Naigowit & Hale, 2008). There is also a strong correlation between organizational identity, OI and organizational commitment (Michael & Bruch, 2006). OI is also a very important process in helping individuals to work for the benefit of the organization. There is also a strong correlation between OI and employee commitment (Edwards, 2005). While another study showed that the morale of the workers is an important indicator for determining the level of OI, in other words, the higher the morale of the employee, the higher the degree of similarity between the employees of the organization (Schrodt, 2002). Finally, another study indicates that there is a positive relationship between the length of service of individuals and their level of similarity with the organization. In other words, the longer the service is, the greater the level of OI (Schrodt, 2002).

As for the OUP, the literature shows that the academicians' desire to stay in the university is not driven by need and that both academics and administrators want to stay in the university in the sense of allegiance to the university (Tolentino, 2013). While another study showed that there is a difference between individuals in terms of culture, which leads to uneven performance, and therefore a difference in productivity levels (Awadh & Saad, 2013), in addition, the performance of the university professor greatly influences the educational process, which leads to the improvement of graduates and the support of the educational process (Anggraeni, 2013). One study found that some students use lectures online as an alternative to attending lectures. The study also suggested that online lectures can be used as a tool to complement the learning process (Williams et al., 2012). In addition, the skills of faculty members play an important role in students' assessment of the educational process. The study also pointed to the importance and necessity of encouraging the use of teaching aids in education at the university level (Hains-Wesson, 2011). One of the studies found that there are differences between the attitudes of the faculty member and the students towards evaluating the dimensions of the teaching process. The lecturers believe that they performed the teaching process with the required quality. However, the students believe that there are differences between the lecturers in terms of their educational performance (Hsu & Chiu, 2009). Finally, another study indicates that faculty members who have good relationships with students are better evaluated than others. Faculty members who seek to interest and absorb students are highly evaluated and have characteristics that enable them to accommodate students (Best & Addison, 2000).

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between OI and OUP.

H1: There is no statistical relationship between OI (OL) and OUP at Sadat City University.

H2: OI (OS) has no statistically significant effect on OUP at Sadat City University in Egypt.

H3: There is no statistical relationship between OI (OM) and OUP at Sadat City University.

7. Research Population

The research population at SCU is 801 employees. Due to the small number of the research community, it was decided to use complete numeration or census) to get the highest percentage of survey lists The research population is illustrated in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Faculty Members	Number	Percentage
1. Faculty of Veterinary Medicine	154	19%
2. Faculty of Tourism & Hotels	93	12%
3. Genetic Engineering Research Institute	124	16%
4. Faculty of Physical Education	186	23%
5. Faculty of Education	49	6%
6. Faculty of Commerce	69	9%
7. Faculty of Law	59	7%
8. Institute for Environmental Studies and Research	50	6%
9. Faculty of Pharmacy	17	2%
Total	801	100%

Source: Staff Members Affairs Department, SCU, Egypt, 2018

Table (2) provides features of items of the sample at Sadat City University in Egypt.

Table (2) Frequency Distribution Table of Demographics

Variables	Number	Percentage	
1- Sex	Male	165	52%
	Female	135	48%
	Total	300	100%
2- The Academic Degree	Professor degree	51	17%
	Associate professor	72	24%
	Assistant professor	96	32%
	Lecturer	30	10%
	Demonstrator	51	17%
	Total	300	100%
3- Marital Status	Married	225	75%
	Single	75	25%
	Total	300	100%
4- Age	Less than 30 years	45	15%
	From 30 to 45	135	45%
	More than 45	120	40%
	Total	300	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	144	48%
	From 5 to 10	99	33%
	More than 10	57	19%
	Total	300	100%

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

8. Data Collection

The researcher has used the questionnaire for collecting data. The questionnaire is interested in OI and OUP at SCU. The survey included three questions. The first is related to OI, the second detects OUP, and the third relates to the demographic variables of employees at SCU. About 400 questionnaires were distributed. 300 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 75%. The research depends on the Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

9. Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

9.1. Coding of variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3)
Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables	Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	OL	7	Cheney, 1982
	OS	7	
	OM	9	
	Total Measurement	23	
Dependent Variable	Beneficiaries	3	Kotler, 2000
	Processes	3	
	Resources	3	
	OC	3	
	Total Measurement	12	

9.2. Construct Validity

The researcher depends on the method of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. CFA was applied to the research variables as follows:

9.2.1. Organizational Identification

The researcher used CFA for OI which consists of three dimensions. They are OL, OS, and OM. The total number of OI is 23 statement. This can be illustrated by a figure (2).

Figure (2)
CFA For OI

According to figure (2), it is clear that all the statement of OI is greater than 0.50, which corresponds to GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. The researcher relies on structural equation (SEM) model because it is the best way to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. The quality indicators for OI variable can be illustrated in the following table:

Table (4)
Quality Indicators for the OI Using AMOS Analysis

Test the Quality of the Model Acceptance Condition ^(*)	Test Value
X ² / Degree of freedom < 5	1807.351
P. value > 0.5	0.000
Goodness of fit Index (GFI) > 0.90	0.661
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI) > 0.95	0.701
Comparative Fit Index (CFI) > 0.95	0.732
Normed Fit Index (NFI) > 0.90	0.706
Incremental Fit Index (IFI) > 0.95	0.733

^(*) Daire et al., 2008

In light of the above indicators, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

9.2.2. Outstanding University Performance

The researcher used CFA for OUP which consists of four dimensions. They are beneficiaries, processes, resources, and OC. The total number of OUP is 12 statement. This can be illustrated by the following figure:

Figure (3)
CFA For OUP

From the previous figure, it is clear that all the statement of OUP is greater than 0.50, which corresponds to GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. The researcher depends on SEM because it is one of the best ways to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. The quality indicators for OUP variable can be illustrated in the following table:

Table (5)
Quality Indicators for the OUP Using AMOS Analysis

Test the Quality of the Model Acceptance Condition ^(*)	Test Value
X ² / Degree of freedom < 5	1794.727
P. value > 0.5	0.000
Goodness of fit Index (GFI) > 0.90	0.712
Tuker-Lewis Index (TLI) > 0.95	0.539
Comparative Fit Index (CFI) > 0.95	0.664
Normed Fit Index (NFI) > 0.90	0.660
Incremental Fit Index (IFI) > 0.95	0.666

(*) Daire et al., 2008

In light of the above indicators, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

9.3. Descriptive Analysis

Table (6): shows the mean and standard deviations of OI and OUP

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
OI	OL	4.02	0.652
	OS	4.01	1.01
	OM	4.15	0.756
	Total Measurement	4.06	0.613
OUP	Beneficiaries	4.25	0.635
	Processes	2.97	1.11
	Resources	3.41	0.923
	OC	3.46	0.877
	Total Measurement	3.55	0.619

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

According to Table (6), among the various facets of OI, most of the respondents identified the presence of OL ($M=4.02$, $SD=0.652$), OS ($M=4.01$, $SD=1.01$), and OM ($M=4.15$, $SD=0.756$), total OI ($M=4.06$, $SD=0.613$).

The second issue examined was the different facets of OUP. Most of the respondents identified the presence of beneficiaries ($M=4.25$, $SD=0.635$), processes ($M=2.97$, $SD=1.11$), resources ($M=3.41$, $SD=0.923$), and OC ($M=3.46$, $SD=0.877$), total OUP ($M=3.55$, $SD=0.619$).

9.4. Evaluating Reliability

Table (7): Reliability of OI and OUP

Variables	Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
OI	OL	7	0.841
	OS	7	0.947
	OM	9	0.918
	Total Measurement	23	0.921
OUP	Beneficiaries	3	0.742
	Processes	3	0.976
	Resources	3	0.849
	OC	3	0.832
	Total Measurement	12	0.879

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (7) presents the reliability of OI. The reliabilities of OL, OS, and OM are generally higher. OI are reliable because ACC is 0.921. OL is reliable because ACC is 0.841. OS are reliable because ACC is 0.947 while OM are reliable because ACC is 0.918. Thus, the internal consistency of OI can be acceptable.

Also, OUP are reliable because ACC is 0.879. Beneficiaries is reliable because ACC is 0.742. The processes are reliable because ACC is 0.976 while the resources are reliable because ACC is 0.849. OC is reliable because ACC is 0.832. Thus, the internal consistency of OUP can be acceptable.

9.5. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (8): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	OI	OUP
OI	4.06	0.613	1	
OUP	3.55	0.619	0.625**	1

Source: PSS, V.23, 2015

Regarding Table (8), the level of OI is high (Mean=4.06; SD=0.613), while OUP is (Mean=3.55; SD=0.619). The overall correlation between OI and OUP is 0.625.

9.6. The Correlation between OI and OUP

The relationship between OI and OUP at SCU is presented in the following table:

Table (9): Correlation Matrix between OI and OUP

Research Variables	1	2	3	4
OL	1			
OS	0.411**	1		
OM	0.256**	0.422**	1	
OUP	0.489**	0.479**	0.472**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (9), the correlation between OI (OL) and OUP is 0.489. For OI (OS) and OUP, the value is 0.479 whereas OI (OM) and OUP shows correlation value of 0.472. The overall correlation between OI and OUP is 0.625.

9.7. Organizational Identification (OL) and OUP

The relationship between OI (OL) and OUP is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between OI (OL) and OUP at Sadat City University

Table (10): MRA Results for OI (OL) and OUP

The Variables of OI (OL)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I defend this university and its policies against other.	0.184**	0.385	0.148
2. I feel annoyed when others criticize the university unobjectively.	0.007	0.341	0.116
3. I believe the achievements of the university are a source of pride for its staff.	0.177*	0.418	0.174
4. I like to speak to others about the successful projects of the university.	0.029	0.352	0.123
5. I feel continual loyalty towards the SCU.	0.239**	0.408	0.166
6. I am proud of being one of the personnel of this university.	0.132*	0.354	0.125
7. Generally, I am interested in the future of this university.	0.087	0.223	0.049
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F 		0.531 0.282 16.364 7, 292 2.63	
** P < .01 * P < .05			

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (10) proves that there is a relationship between OI (OL). It represents 53%, according to MCC. Also, OI (OL) may interpret about 28% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant statistical impact of OI (OL) on OUP. The alternative hypothesis has been accepted because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between OI (OL) and OUP according to T-test (See table 10).

9.8. Organizational Identification (OS) and OUP

The relationship between OI (OS) and OUP is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: OI (OS) has no significant effect on OUP at Sadat City University in Egypt.

Table (11) proves that there is a relationship between OI (OS). It represents 57%, according to MCC. Also, OI (OS) may interpret about 33% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between OI (OS) and OUP according to T-test (See table 11).

Table (11) MRA Results for OI (OS) and OUP

The Variables of OI (OS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I do my utmost for the university to attain its goals.	0.555**	0.499	0.249
2. I work at SCU to achieve its mission.	0.539**	0.525	0.275
3. The image of the university in the community is identical to my orientations and expectations.	0.071	0.331	0.109
4. I try to take decisions at work avoiding the ones that negatively affect the university.	0.289*	0.399	0.159
5. Generally, I believe the problems of the university are mine.	0.082	0.505	0.255
6. I accept the policies of the university regarding important issues related to my affairs.	0.281**	0.309	0.101
7. I believe my values and those of the university are highly similar.	0.015	0.349	0.121
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F 		0.576 0.332 20.736 7, 292 2.63	
** P < .01 * P < .05			

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

9.9. Organizational Identification (OM) and OUP

The relationship between OI (OM) and OUP is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between OI (OM) and OUP at Sadat City University

Table (12): MRA Results for OI (OM) and OUP

The Variables of OI OM	Beta	R	R ²
1. I feel greatly pleased about working at the university.	0.049	0.368	0.135
2. I have to belong to the SCU where I work.	0.157*	0.487	0.237
3. I feel my future plans, and those of the university are identical.	0.132	0.457	0.208
4. I may describe the SCU as a big family.	0.318**	0.500	0.250
5. There are many common situations with others who work at the university.	0.131	0.376	0.141
6. I easily decide my identity through the university.	0.225**	0.411	0.168
7. I hope I will keep on working at the university even if I do not need the salary.	0.143*	0.175	0.030
8. I feel the SCU pays much attention to me.	0.078	0.305	0.093
9. I describe myself to others saying "I work at the university," "I am from the university."	0.088	0.316	0.099
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F 		0.579 0.335 16.255 9, 290 2.40	
** P < .01 * P < .05			

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (12) proves that there is a relationship between OI (OM). It represents 57%, according to MCC. Also, OI (OM) may interpret about 33% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis which states that there is no impact of OI (OM) on OUP. The alternative hypothesis has been accepted because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between OI (OM). and OUP according to T-test (See table 12).

10. Research Results

1. The general average of the areas of OI among the different categories of faculty members at SCU is high. The OM as one of the dimensions of OI ranked first, followed by OL in the second place, and finally the OS in the third place as one of the dimensions of OI at SCU.
2. The general average of the areas of job performance among the various categories of faculty members at SCU is high. The beneficiaries as one of the dimensions of OUP ranked first, followed by the OC in the second place, the resources in the third place, and finally the process as one of the dimensions of OUP at SCU.
3. There is a statistically significant relationship between the areas of OI (OL, OS, and OM), and OUP (beneficiaries, process, resources, and OC) at SCU.
4. The researcher used CFA in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. It is clear that all the statement of OI and OUP are greater than 0.50, which corresponds to the GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. The researcher depended on the SEM because it is one of the best ways to use the multivariable test. SEM has been used to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. In order to ascertain whether the model is compatible with the sample data used. Also, it already measures the variable that should be measured. It is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

11. Recommendations

1. Designing and implementing a set of training programs for all officials at SCU to maintain the level of OI among faculty members, and this can be done through the development of awareness among administrative leaders of the concept and importance and areas of OI and its positive effects both at the level of faculty member, or at the university level, where OI contributes significantly to the improvement of the level of ambition among faculty members, increase the affiliation and loyalty to the university, and increase the degree of commitment to work, and increase the degree of cohesion and cooperation, participation, coordination, and ease of communication between them, increasing the degree of correlation with the values and objectives of the university, and contribute effectively to the achievement of its objectives, and work for its benefit, and the desire to OM, and continue to serve, and increase the effort at work, And deepen the behavior of organizational citizenship, and thus improve the performance of faculty members at SCU.
2. The officials at SCU maintain the level of OI, and can be done by increasing interest in faculty members, and meet their needs and desires periodically to achieve and satisfy the possible ones, and that the administrative leaders at SCU to clarify the objectives which the University seeks to achieve, and to involve faculty members in identifying and setting them up.
3. The officials at SCU should increase the level of OI among faculty members, and can be done by inviting members of the faculty to participate in decision-making by providing their views and suggestions, as the process of participation in decision-making gives it the status realism, and creates motivation for them to implement the decision seriously because of their sense that the decision is their decision whether it is at the departmental, college or university level.
4. Directing the attention of officials at SCU to strengthen the OI among faculty members, and can be done through meetings and meetings, and the practice of social and recreational activities, which leads to greater cohesion and interdependence among faculty members and create effectiveness among them.
5. The officials at SCU should maintain on the level of performance of all members of the faculty, and to support and strengthen the strengths, and address the causes of weakness and weakness and work to avoid them in the future.
6. Directing the attention of officials at SCU should maintain the level of OI among faculty members, and can be done through the creation of working conditions, and follow the method of incentives, whether physical or moral, and the design of incentive systems conditional on performance, as the incentives play an important role in maintaining the level of OI on the one hand and positively affecting the level of functional performance on the other.

11. Future research proposals

This research is concerned with analyzing the relationship between organizational symmetry and functional performance. There is a large number of proposals that need further study and analysis, such as OS and its impact on some variables such as functional empowerment, organizational justice, OC, organizational citizenship, etc. These studies can be applied to other societies such as private universities, education directorates, as well as public and private hospitals.

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